

Neutrinos, Neutron Stars, and Axions

Spiraling Around the Central Topic of Electric Current on Stellar, Nebular,
Galactic, and Supra-galactic Scales

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ABSTRACT

Axions and neutrinos represent “well-motivated” models in the search for Cold Dark Matter. However, both are being constrained repeatedly by the actual search process. Also, in the discussion of exotic matter, neutron star behavior demonstrates unequivocal electromagnetic behavior which favors not gravitational collapse but Marklund convection as a means of pulsar generation. With several legs of the Standard Model (SM) failing under the Big Bang Cosmological family of astrophysics, plasma related cosmological paradigms stand to gain much advancement from the work of projects like NuSTAR, ADMX, and NICER. However, careful review of the data will be needed to look out for attempted obfuscations or excuse-making which yields good data useless in the hands of a throw-away cosmogony. Instead, it is best to utilize the research for confirmative purposes in the Plasma-electromagnetic paradigms.

Keywords: Axion - Neutrino - Neutron Stars - Magnetic Current - Dark Matter

Updates on Neutrino//Dark Matter Search

Only recently, the author reviewed one proposal to search for acoustic shockwaves generating neutrino decay.¹ The author had a fairly favorable opinion of this search proposal. The quoted author also clarified, in communications with this author,

“The neutrinos I am searching for would have been the result of the decay of neutrons or neutron-like particles. By now, the kinetic energy of those neutrinos would have diminished to less than 1 electron volt as space expanded... akin to the diminished photonic energy of the CMB.

“I propose exploring the dynamic physical properties of the medium of space first. The more we explore them while engaging the effects, the cleaner will be the path to later understanding its composition. We are looking for primordial relic neutrinos as evidence of primordial relic neutron disintegrations. When using the word acoustics, it does not mean 'sound' as in the ordinary sense. Shockwaves can be sound as in air or water pressure waves. They can also be in any sort of medium.... The neutrino kinetic energies should show a similar expansion degradation like the CMB from their initial 0.782343 MeV to less than 1 e-Volt.” ~W. Giordano, via email

Since then, however, a paper was released that further constrained “Sterile Neutrino Dark Matter,”

*“We use a combined 1.2 Ms of NuSTAR observations of M31 to search for X-ray lines from sterile neutrino dark matter decay... **We find no evidence of unknown lines**, and thus derive limits on the sterile neutrino parameters. Our results place stringent constraints for **dark matter masses ≥ 12 keV**, which reduces the available parameter space for sterile neutrino dark matter produced via neutrino mixing (e.g., in the ν MSM) by approximately one-third.”²*

That pretty much sums itself up (excellent abstract). The paper is complicated, and summarizes the NuSTAR team’s efforts. Actually they found constraints as low as 5 keV, but set the main constraints at 12-20 keV, though they went as high as 100 keV. But as discussed in part 5, “Dark Matter Scatter,”³ the goal may be to eliminate small ranges, in a kind of “keep away” game that realistically has no end. Nevertheless, for now, the neutrino discussion is effectively [partially] neutralized.

Neutron Star research pile-drives itself into PEMC

As mentioned in the last paper, as well, DM research has not inhibited PEMC (though it hasn’t been the most efficient way to do the research, financially speaking and timewise). But it is, nevertheless, frustrating when the research in the Standard Model (SM), within Big Bang tries to skirt around the issue of Birkeland Currents, and (like a trapeze artist riding a unicycle balancing plates on poles on their nose) attempts to explain the return currents while hand-waving and calling it magnetic flux ropes, magnetic currents (a sure misnomer), and distracting the reader from the obvious question: **how can neutral material generate charge separation!?**

They immediately answer, in a new paper that is as close to forehead smacking as SM gets,

*“The primary targets are isolated, **rotation-powered pulsars**, in which the surface polar caps are heated by bombardment from magnetospheric currents of electrons and positrons.”⁴*

¹ [13]

² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.01262.pdf>

³ [16]

⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.01274.pdf>

The paper by the NICER team, once you get passed the assumptions, hubris⁵, and missteps⁶ ... an excellent PEMC paper, masquerading as a BBC paper:

"2. CHARGED PARTICLE ENERGY LOSSES IN A PLASMA

Energetic electrons and positrons can interact with the particles of a plasma in several different ways. They can scatter directly off both the electrons and the ions in the plasma, or **they can excite plasma waves**. Additionally, particles can lose energy via the emission of Bremsstrahlung radiation as they pass near ions in the plasma. In this section, we will discuss the dominant interaction mechanisms and calculate the energy loss rate of both electrons and positrons traveling through a hydrogen plasma. **The return current electrons and positrons we consider here are moderately to highly relativistic** ($\gamma \sim 2$ to $\gamma \sim 500$). The electrons in the neutron-star atmosphere, in contrast, have **energies near 1 keV**, corresponding to $\gamma \sim 1.004$. Therefore, we can make the assumption that the **plasma electrons and ions are essentially stationary compared to the return current particles**. The first channel for energy loss is via binary interactions with the free electrons (Møller scattering or Bhabha scattering for electrons and positrons, respectively) and the ions in the plasma. Since the cross-section for the scattering interaction is inversely proportional to the mass of the target, **we neglect the electron-ion and positron-ion scattering terms and calculate only the scattering with the plasma electrons**. In addition to direct scattering, the relativistic particles excite collective plasma modes (Langmuir waves) and thereby transmit additional energy to the atmosphere. Direct scattering and excitation of **Langmuir waves dominate the energy loss rate for particles passing through a neutron star atmosphere.**" p.3 (emphasis added)

Figure 1: proposed neutron

Firstly, the author would like to remind the reader of the likely incorrect model of the nucleus of the atom.⁷ While we understand the behaviors of the valence shells and probabilistic wave-functions governing discrete quantized behavior in a QED/QDM model of the atom... in all likelihood the SM understanding of the nucleus is flat out wrong.⁸ The author, therefore, favors the Structured Atom Model (SAM)

⁵ "One of the key results of these studies has been that accurate interpretation of the pulse profiles [did we send a probe?] relies on a good understanding of the properties of the stellar atmosphere [doubtful, since spectrology is an art, and there's almost no good understanding of our own star, let alone distant ones] and, in particular, on the dependence of the emitted spectrum of radiation on the angle from the normal to the stellar surface." p.2 (emphasis added)

The author can think of no instance in science or regular life where you can arrive at certain truth from **only an orthogonal perspective**.

⁶ "There has been, however, no effort so far to calculate the temperature profile of the bombarded neutron-star atmosphere and the resulting spectrum and beaming of the surface emission... The physics of radiative cooling in[side] neutron-star atmospheres is well understood..." p. 2

The atmospheres of our planets are not well understood... our own atmosphere is not "well understood!" What an absurd and asinine statement, very arrogant of the authors!

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sJKW9VNo2BU>

⁸ Just as the photon is **definitely** wrong, see [12]

⁹. Firstly this means that “neutrons” are merely a shorthand for electron-proton¹⁰ close orbits¹¹ (and hence the higher order of magnitude of force, as measured in energy, for the “Strong Force” and “Weak Force”). See Figure 1. Granted, this would require that the remaining mass (not inertia, but energy) would need to be found in terms of the charge, not merely in subtraction but in actual measurement of the inside of the neutron. So far, this has not materialized. To the author, this is only a matter of time and improvement in QEM.

What needs to be focused on, however, is the glaring obviousness of the above discussion. They are describing electric currents, and **calling them magnetic currents**. Let’s be clear: magnetism itself does not “flow”, it waves, and concentrates or dilutes. When one speaks of magnetic flux, such as in a transformer, it must be born in mind this is a model, a device. But if one uses iron filings, magnetic fields may alternate but they are not flowing, and the filings will not move with the field. It is a mathematical concept from Maxwell/Gauss. In magnetohydrodynamics, magnetism is treated like a fluid, and thus made to flow, but this is still after all a model of convenience, as stated also by Alfvén himself. The fact is that the actual flow is electrical. Electric currents are found to be flowing in and out of AGN¹², black holes, stars, planets, etc...

What is disturbing about this trend is that, despite evidence showing that such “magnetic flux ropes” (Birkeland currents) are shown to not be *directly* powered by Saturnian or Jovian rotation^{13 14}, but by internal currents and magneto-motive moments.¹⁵ The cores, and their reaction with the atmospheres and the solar wind, appear to be the source of the currents. Yet, in pulsars, the mechanism is supposed to be rotation. But, neutrons have no mechanism for sudden accumulation¹⁶ and no reason for mutual attraction.¹⁷ Furthermore pulsars rotate excessively fast¹⁸ which will not work for accumulation models without excessively ridiculous gravitational forces¹⁹ that make little sense, given the energy absorption and discharge rate. A transistor model, which is a natural Scottian electric stellar model derivation, will much more easily account for increasing frequency discoveries, as well as “impossible” phenomena such as repetitive novae and supernovae²⁰, micronovae²¹, and dwarf flares²².

Where does this leave the SM/BBC? Dangling against the ropes. When a huge stilt upon which your astrophysical “concrete” theory rests upon abandons one model for clear (albeit apparently embarrassed) admission of a superior and simpler model... that leaves a gaping hole in the “armor” of the SM. One which DM

⁹ <https://etherealmatters.org/sites/default/files/2018-02/Presentation%20SAM%202017.pdf>

¹⁰ “Positron emission or beta plus decay (β^+ decay) is a subtype of radioactive decay called beta decay, in which a proton inside a radionuclide nucleus is converted into a neutron while releasing a positron and an electron neutrino (ν_e). Positron emission is mediated by the weak force.” https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Positron_emission

Conversely it could also be said that since a pulsar is a region where charge (via plasma) is being compressed into an ultra-compact transistor-like plasmoid, which is receiving and quickly discharging more and more protons, that of course it would *appear* to be made of neutrons through electron and positron release... but actually it is made of protons which are throwing out massive amounts of gamma rays. This is, of course, spectrally proven.

¹¹ <https://vimeo.com/212131985>

¹² <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/2041-8205/788/1/L19/pdf>

¹³ <https://www.bas.ac.uk/media-post/a-new-way-to-create-saturns-radiation-belts/>

¹⁴ <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1700040>

¹⁵ So-called “dynamo” mechanisms (a misnomer as well, as dynamos are DC related generators)

¹⁶ Literally gases cannot compress spontaneously in a vacuum without violating thermodynamics.

¹⁷ Literally no charge to attract, according to their model. Conversely, plasma has a reason for a pileup of charge, so-called Marklund Convection: <https://youtu.be/sIQRBrmEIXo>

¹⁸ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn8576-fast-spinning-neutron-star-smashes-speed-limit/>

¹⁹ https://www.researchgate.net/post/Why_dont_fast_spinning_stars_dont_explode

²⁰ <https://news.sky.com/story/zombie-star-baffles-scientists-by-surviving-supernovae-11119311>

²¹ <https://www.exopolitics.org/impending-solar-flash-event-supported-by-scientific-studies-insider-testimony/>

²² <https://www.iflscience.com/space/dwarf-star-emits-solar-flare-10000-times-stronger-anything-seen-our-sun/>

failures, SUSY and MOND quasi-quackery (see Table 2), and no amount of BEC's and neutrinos can make up for. Eventually, the resulting question forms on everyone's mind, "Isn't an electric universe and plasma/covert matter model a lot simpler and more coherent?"

Yes.

For more reason why SM cosmologists should consider switching to E/PEMC, see the author's previous works.²³

Axions are Oxymorons

In the final paper by the ADMX team examined in this part 6 breakdown, a re-hashed "promising" Dark Matter is once again proposed. Axions have fallen out of favor in many sectors, and aren't well understood despite being around since 1977 (see Table 1). They are, after all, rather oxymoronic,

*"Given that the dark matter density within our own Milky Way halo is expected to be $\rho_a \approx 0.45 \text{ GeV/cm}^3$ [15], dark matter axions would have a **local number density** $\sim 10^{14}/\text{cm}^3$, but would remain almost impossible to detect due to their weak coupling.²⁴ To date, the most promising detection scheme is the "axion haloscope" which exploits the inverse Primakoff effect [16]. In this scheme, a high-Q, tunable microwave cavity is immersed in a strong magnetic field. Dark matter axions interact with the static magnetic field, **convert to photons**, and deposit energy into the resonant mode of the cavity"²⁵*

The author has a *number* of problems with the above schemata.

1. That is incredibly difficult to believe density, considering there is zero evidence in our own local matter to justify such an existence. It is really very difficult to believe this is anything more than a mathematical invention - a figment of imagination - not any better than the proposed strings.
2. It doesn't interact because it is 'weak' (undefined), and only proposed to interact if there is a magnetic field 'strong' enough (also undefined). If a black hole, quasar, or AGN isn't strong enough, the author reiterates nothing will be, could be, or ever would be, which makes them not "theoretically detectible" but "practicably invisible forever." It's another unicorn search.
3. If they cannot find them, why postulate that they turn into photons? This is, in the author's opinion, to bolster a presumed connection to the SM. The irony is that, since the photonic model is incomplete or even broken, it will do not good. This is essentially modern sorcery. There isn't enough anima to meet the materia? What is the point of all of this speculation?

The paper goes on to describe a method of using "piezoelectrically tuned multimode cavities" for the detection process. Apparently the Sidecar cryostat is housing an 8.5 T (wow!) magnet fabricated at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory²⁶. The paper then goes through a detailed description of *how hard it was*, but it finally comes to the point,

*"Each residual spectrum is then divided by its fit and the baseline of 1 was subtracted to yield unitless spectra with zero mean. **Axion-like signals were added to the data** to measure the degree of sensitivity degradation caused by the fit."* (emphasis added)²⁷

²³ [1] & [17]

²⁴ A plethora of them but can't find a single one. What's worse is, it's local and not some distant object. That should render it much easier to find, right? Wrong. This is why axions have not been favored. They are a mathematical prediction of a physical problem.

²⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1901.00920.pdf>

²⁶ More irrelevant fiddle-faddle to establish officiality and authority.

²⁷ p.4

*“In summary, the ADMX Sidecar has produced new limits on the axion coupling factor in three frequency bands within the range 4.2 GHz–7.2 GHz. This is the first time an axion haloscope has been operated over much of this region and improves on the solar bounds [42] by two orders of magnitude under the assumption of 100% dark matter axion-like particles. While **this sensitivity is not sufficient to reach the axion coupling predicted for QCD axions**, it excludes a meaningful $g_{a\gamma\gamma}$ parameter space for generically motivated axions, and spearheads experimental efforts for DFSZ sensitivity in this axion mass range.”*

In other words, the equipment can't work, and as stated before likely won't work. They have plans to continue - of course- but it is a fancy paper saying fancily that once again: Dark Matter is nowhere to be found.

Table 1 :: Proper Physics Chronology²⁸

Electricity	Ben Franklin	1751
Gaussian Theory	Carl Gauss	1813
Electromagnetism Unification	Michael Faraday	1831
Doppler Redshift	Hippolyte Fizeau	1848
Maxwell's Equations	James Maxwell	1861-62
Quantized Hypothesis	Ludwig Boltzmann	1877
Photoelectric effect	Heinrich Hertz	1887
Electron Theory	JJ Thomson	1897
Quantum Theory	Max Planck	1900
Relativity theory	Henri Poincare	1900-1904
Mass-energy relation	Henri Poincare	1900
Gravity Waves	Henri Poincare	1905
Special Relativity	Albert Einstein	1905
Photoelectric Effect Explained	Albert Einstein	1905
Birkeland Currents	Kristian Birkeland	1908
Atomic Theory Proved	Ernest Rutherford	1911
Particle-Wave Theory of Atoms and Particles	Niels Bohr	1913
General Relativity	Albert Einstein	1915
Proton discovered	Ernest Rutherford	1919
Quantum Radiation Interaction	Paul Dirac	1920
Quantum Mechanics Codified	Born, Heisenberg, Pauli	1924
Bose-Einstein Condensate	Bose, Einstein	1924
Plasma Cosmology	Irving Langmuir	1927
Big Bang Cosmology	Georges Lemaitre	1927
Missing Matter	Edward Zwicky	1933
Magnetohydrodynamics	Hannes Alfven	1940
QEM/QED	Bethe to Feynman	1947-1960
Electroweak Theory	JC Ward	1959
Quarks	M Gell-Mann & G Zweig	1964
Black Hole Theory	John Wheeler	1967
Dark Matter	Rubin & Ford	1970
Electric Star Theory	Ralph Juergens ²⁹	1972
QCD	Gross, Wilczek, & Politzer	1973
Axions	Peicci & Quinn	1977
SUSY	Werner Nahm	1978
WIMPs	unclear ³⁰	1980
MOND	Mordehai Milgrom	1982
String Theory	Green & Schwarz	1984
Dark Energy	Friedman ³¹ or Sivaram ³²	1924 or 1986
M Theory	Edward Witten	1995
Intrinsic Redshift	Halton Arp ³³	1998

²⁸ Tables 1 and 2 reproduced from [11]; all references in [13] included, as this paper is a follow-up.

²⁹ https://www.velikovsky.info/Ralph_Juergens

³⁰ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/dark-matter-exotic-possibilities/>

³¹ <http://home.fnal.gov/~skent/early.html>

³² <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/0809/0809.3364.pdf>

³³ https://www.haltonarp.com/articles/intrinsic_redshifts_in_quasars_and_galaxies.pdf

Table 2 :: Falsifications

SUSY	2012 ³⁶ - 2017 ³⁷
CDM	2012 ³⁸ , 2015 ³⁹ , 2016 ⁴⁰ - 2018 ^{41 42 43 44}
ΛCDM	2010 ⁴⁵ , 2014 ⁴⁶
WIMPs & MACHOs	2017 ⁴⁷
MOND	2018 ^{48 49 50}
Galaxy Rotation and DM	2017 ^{51 52}
Standard Redshift	2017 ^{53 54 55}
Galaxy Rotation and MOND	2018 ⁵⁶
Higgs-boson as non-standard Quark	2018 ⁵⁷
Dark Energy	2018 ⁵⁸
LDM	2018 ⁵⁹

Conclusion

The progress made so far in the Dark Matter search has been to confirm the electro-plasma Universe, rather than a non-baryonic Dark Universe. In some of the previous papers, there were mere axiomatic or ideological differences between the topics (such as with BEC's and ultracold plasma). But in most of the searches, clear philosophical divisions have created demonstrable separations which define the difference between a PEMC and BBC/SM vision of reality. In this paper neutrinos and axions were reviewed in new literature which demonstrated their severe constraints. Philosophical and logical conundrums were underlined. Furthermore a neutron-star paper was reviewed and demonstrated to have a strange amount of hubris for being a fantastic reference piece not for the Standard Model, but for alternative Plasma Cosmological models.

³⁴ <http://www.astro.caltech.edu/~george/ay20/ea-wimps-machos.pdf>

³⁵ <https://theconversation.com/from-machos-to-wimps-meet-the-top-five-candidates-for-dark-matter-51516>

³⁶ <http://backreaction.blogspot.com/2016/08/the-lhc-nightmare-scenario-has-come-true.html>

³⁷ <https://www.space.com/39001-dark-matter-doesnt-exist-study-suggests.html>

³⁸ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1204.2546>

³⁹ http://adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/bib_query?arXiv:1406.4860

⁴⁰ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2016arXiv161003854K>

⁴¹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.09823.pdf>

⁴² <https://academic.oup.com/mnras/article/476/3/3124/4875952>

⁴³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1807.07113.pdf>

⁴⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.04817.pdf>

⁴⁵ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1011.0004>

⁴⁶ https://astro.uni-bonn.de/~pavel/kroupa_SciLogs.html

⁴⁷ <https://phys.org/news/2017-12-machos-dead-wimps-no-shows-simps.html>

⁴⁸ <https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/falsifications-and-constraints-due-to-gw-measurements.929254/>

⁴⁹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.04167.pdf>

⁵⁰ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1809/1809.09019.pdf>

⁵¹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.10706.pdf>

⁵² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08843.pdf>

⁵³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.03298.pdf>

⁵⁴ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.09409>

⁵⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.03888.pdf>

⁵⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1801.09304.pdf>

⁵⁷ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-06130-9>

⁵⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.05027.pdf>

⁵⁹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.10543.pdf>

Some overlap with the SM is demonstrable, but it is established with *apriori* authority that is betrayed by the actual work shown. On all scales: the Universe is, after all, electro-magnetic.

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